

ARCHITECTURE AND LANDSCAPE OF FERGANA CITY

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ANNOTATSIYA

This article covers the full response to modern urban planning requirements of new Uzbekistan, industrial zones, residential and non-residential areas, public spaces, location of transport and vehicles, urban ecology, urban landscape and architecture.

Key words: *Industrial zones, urban planning, modernity, ecology, residences, public, landscape solutions.*

The Republic of Uzbekistan has given each field considerable attention starting in the year of independence. Modern city development, the establishment of amenities for people, the layout of residential high-rises, and urban design are a few examples. The Republic of Uzbekistan's Law No. 174-I on "Architecture and Urban Planning" was passed on December 22, 1995. Numerous opportunities have arisen during the implementation and execution of this law, and it was on this basis that the national-state "Construction norms and regulations" were developed, taking into account the historical and cultural assets, climate, earthquake risk, and other general conditions unique to our territory. It is important to remember that urban development has received attention ever since the first year of independence. The "New Uzbekistan" massif, which is being constructed in Fergana, is a prime illustration of this. [1]

There are several cities in Uzbekistan, including Toshloq district, Margilon, Yozyovon, and Quva, which arose as a result of the country's rapid industrial

development and concurrent population increase. In the case of the city of Fergana, we can clearly discern the intricate manner of urban rehabilitation. The founder of the Babur dynasty, poet, historian, geographer, statesman, and skilled general Zahiriddin Muhammad ibn Umarshaikh Mirza (Babur), said about the Fergana region: "Fergana region is the fifth climate... Eastern Kashkar, gHe didn't just characterize Samarkand in the east, Badakhshan in the south, and the cities in the north as mountains for no reason. [3]

One of the finest states in American history is regarded as being this one. They have been farming here on the foothills of the Qurama and Qoramozor mountains for a very long time. The vulture horses that were produced in this valley have proliferated all over the world. Chinese emperors were particularly interested in the horses of this valley. They even gave the term "Celestial" to one of the horse breeds. "Heavenly horses" had power and dexterity. The material in the Chinese annals was supported by evidence discovered by archaeologists. Davan grew into a highly developed state in the II and I centuries BC thanks to its vast population, well-equipped military, and skilled police force. Shorabashat and Uchkurgan residents, for example, have had remarkable success cultivating the land, raising wheat and rice, and growing grapes. Scientists believe that the Davan state fell in the third century AD. This state was known as Fergana at the start of the Middle Ages. The "Ixshid" were Ferghana's monarchs. Ferghana's plains are exceedingly fertile, and its citizens relied on farming to support themselves by sowing rice and cotton. A variety of handicrafts have grown in popularity both domestically and abroad thanks to the development of these industries in major central cities including Koson, Axsikat, and Quva. Exports to the surrounding nations included paint, colorful glass items, and pharmaceuticals. Sahibgiron Amir Temur's rule marked the rise of this state at the start of the Middle Ages. [5]

1-Picture. A teapot in the village of Zarkent

Tashloq district was established in the Fergana area in 1935.

It shares boundaries with Quva districts to the east, Quvasoy city to the southeast, Margilon city to the west, Qoshtepa, Yozyovon to the northwest, and Boz district of Andijan region to the northeast.

There are 0.24 thousand km² there. As of October 1, 2021, there are 208,700 inhabitants, including

48,200 urban and 160,400 rural citizens.

The district, industrial zones, residential areas, public spaces, and transportation facilities are all flawlessly and logically designed in every way to provide the best working and recreational environments.

REFERENCES

1. Tolibjonovich, T. B. (2023). Replace thermal coatings to maintain room temperature. *Barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 3(2), 164-168.
2. Tolibjonovich, T. B. (2022). Specific Causes of Friction and Vibration. *Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 12, 86-89.
3. Tojiboyev, B. T. (2021). THERMAL STATE OF ENGINE PARTS AND METHODS FOR ITS DETERMINATION. *Scientific progress*, 2(8), 521-527.
4. Tolibjonovich, T. B. (2022). HEAT CONSUMPTION COATS. *American Journal Of Applied Science And Technology*, 2(05), 40-44.
5. Tojiboyev, B. T. (2022). Prospects for the use of Innovative Technologies in the Application of Heat Storage Materials. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 3(5), 1-9.
6. Tolibjonovich, T. B. (2022). МЕТОДЫ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ТЕПЛОВОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ ДЕТАЛЕЙ ДВИГАТЕЛЯ. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 219-225.

7. Tolibjonovich, T. B. (2022). INNOVATIVE MATERIALS WITH HEAT RETENTION. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 155-161.
8. Tolibjonovich, T. B. (2022). LIQUID COMPOSITE THERMAL INSULATION COATINGS AND METHODS FOR DETERMINING THEIR THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY. *International Journal of Advance Scientific Research*, 2(03), 42-50.
9. Tojiboyev, B. T. (2022). Energiya saqlash qobiliyatiga ega issiqlik saqlovchi materiallarni qo'llashda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish istiqbollari. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 186-192.
10. Tojiboyev, B. T. (2022). SLIP PROBLEMS THAT OCCUR DURING ROLLING FRICTION. *INTELLECTUAL EDUCATION TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS AND INNOVATIVE DIGITAL TOOLS*, 1(6), 107-114.
11. Tolibjonovich, T. B. (2022). nabirasi Omongul D. Home-communal on the farm from the heat reasonable use and heat save stay for take being carried out research. *Intellectual education technological solutions and innovative digital tools*, 1(5), 472-478.
12. Tojiboyev, B. T., & Nabirasi, O. D. (2022). Имараттар менен курулмаларда жылуулукту изоляциялоочу каптоолорду колдонуу жана жүргүзүлүп жаткан изилдөөлөр. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(4), 56-62.
13. Tolibjonovich, B. T., & Omongul, D. N. (2022). MÁMLEKETIMIZDE ISSILIQ SAQLAWSHI MATERIALLARǴA BOLǴAN TALAP HÁM OLAR ÚSTINDE ALIP BARILIP ATIRǴAN IZERTLEWLER. *Scientific progress*, 3(1), 24-29.
14. Tojiboyev, B. T. (2022). MODERN HEAT-INSULATING COATING. *Scientific progress*, 3(2), 711-716.
15. TOZHIBOEV, B. T. IZVESTIY OSHSKOGO TECHNOLOGICHESKOGO UNIVERSITY. *IZVESTIY OSHSKOGO TECHNOLOGICHESKOGO UNIVERSITY*

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16. Tojiboyev, B. T. ZAMONAVIY ENERGIYA TEJAMKOR SUYUQ ISSIQLIK SAQLOVCHI QOPLAMALARNI ISSIQLIK O'TKAZUVCHANLIK KOEFFISIENITINI ANIQLASH USULLARI METODY OPREDELENIYA KOEFFISIENITA TEPLOPROVODNOSTI SOVREMENNYX ENERGOEFFEKTIVNYX ZHIDKIX TEPLOZASHITNYX. ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА МАХСУС ТАЪЛИМ ВАЗИРЛИГИ АНДИЖОН МАШИНАСОЗЛИК ИНСТИТУТИ, 32.

17. Tojiboyev, B. T. (2021). Development of thermal insulation materials with low thermal conductivity on the basis of local raw materials. *Scientific progress*, 2(8), 340-346.

18. Tojiboyev, B. T., & Abdubannobova, G. Z. Q. (2021). RECEPTION AND STORAGE OF THE GRAIN MIXTURE COMING AFTER THE HARVESTERS. *Scientific progress*, 2(8), 513-520.

19. Tojiboyev, B. T. (2021). THERMAL STATE OF ENGINE PARTS AND METHODS FOR ITS DETERMINATION. *Scientific progress*, 2(8), 521-527.

20. Tojiboyev, B. T., & Nabirasi, O. M. Q. D. (2021). Heat insulating liquid coating. *Scientific progress*, 2(8), 500-506.

21. Tojiboyev, B. T. (2021). Heat resistant fluid insulating coat. *Scientific progress*, 2(7), 524-531.

22. Tojiboyev, B. T. (2020). Euphemism and gender: Linguocultural euphemisms among males and females in uzbek and english language. *International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education*, 1(5), 8-11.

23. Omongul, D. N. (2021). Definition on the classification of sex euphemisms. *Scientific progress*, 2(7), 532-538.

24. Qizi, D. N. O. M. (2021). Euphemisms In The Speech Of Politicians And Diplomats In Modern English. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(11), 58-64.

25. Qizi, D. N. O. M. (2022). THE USE OF POLITICAL EUPHEMISMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *International Journal of Advance Scientific Research*, 2(12), 53-58.

26. Askarov, X., & Mamajonov, M. (2023). INSHOOT VA BINOLARGA ZILZILA TA'SIRI NATIJASIDA YUKLAR TAHLILI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(6), 12-14.

27. Askarov, X. (2023). SILIKAT MATERIALLARDAN TAYORLANGAN G 'ISHTLARDAN BINO INSHOOTLARINI QURISH TAHLILI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(8), 162-164.

28. Махмудов, С. М. (2021). МОДЕЛИ ГРУНТОВЫХ ОСНОВАНИЙ И ФУНДАМЕНТОВ СОСТОЯЩИХ ИЗ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ ГРУНТОВ.